

Characterization of tobacco leaves in different brands of cigarettes (Indian and Foreign) and their impacts from the social and forensic point of view

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Abstract : Smoking of cigarettes containing tobacco, a widely used delicacy for common masses, has been regarded to be the causes of cancer, heart and a host of other diseases. In spite of extensive researches on tobacco and its different products like nicotine, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, there appears to be a void in the findings. Efforts have been made to make a comparative study on the tobacco and its constituents in different brands of cigarettes ultimately to be related to have some idea on the effectiveness of the filter beds (of cigarettes) in removing nicotine and other hazardous chemicals. Efforts have been made to find out the origin of cigarettes by isotope-ratio monitoring and determining the relative abundances of total isotopes of nicotine (present in tobacco of different brands) using GC-MS and SIM mode of measurements. The observations are also of importance to identify counterfeit cigarettes as well as criminals (a new aspect).

Work is far from complete as no study could be made on smoke condensates. Moreover, all the organic compounds present in tobacco leaves are expected to be converted to ashes at 450 °C. Therefore nicotine and other organic compounds can only be obtained in smoke condensates if the temperature of burning of tobacco is below 450 °C and much less.

Keywords : Cancer, cigarette brands, criminology, counterfeit cigarettes, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), isotope ratio, nicotine, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, SIM.

Introduction

Serious concerns expressing the menace of using tobacco for smoking and non-smoking or smokeless tobacco products like cigarettes, biris, khaini, zarda, gutkhas etc. have been propagated by different health organisations, government and non-government agencies^{1,2}. Both smoking and non-smoking tobacco products are health hazards and shorten the life span due to diseases like chronic destructive lung diseases (COLD), ischemic heart diseases (IHD), myocardial infarction (MI), atherosclerosis, chronic bronchitis, thrombosis, cancer in lungs, oral cavities, larynx, oesophagus, bladder, kidney, pancreas and a lot of other diseases³⁻⁶.

In spite of knowing fully the addictive and deleterious health hazards, smoking is a widely used delicacy to get mental satisfaction. Smoking is supposed to improve mental

functions, enhances alertness, information processing and memory retention^{7,8}. Tobacco smoking (or non-smoking tobacco products) though detrimental, helps business, employment and national economy.

Smoke from the burning tip of cigarette supposed to have a temperature range of 350–900 °C (probably exaggerated) in oxygen deficient conditions, pollutes the body system and ambient air due to distribution of aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons or other constituents. The range of compounds contains C₁₃ to C₃₆ with odd to even carbon predominance; maximum values are C₂₇–C₃₃ with n-dotriacontane (C₃₂ – straight chain compound). There are more high molecular weight polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) like naphthalene, acenaphthalene, acenaphthene, fluorene, phenanthrene, fluoranthrene, benzo(α)pyrene (BAP – carcinogenic bio-indicator),

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crysene, benzo(α ,p)anthracene, benzo(α ,p,i)-perylene, terpenes, phytosterols, pesticides etc.^{9,10}.

Among the list of large number compounds, chemicals like CO and HCN, butadiene, benzene, acrolein, aromatic amines like 4-aminobiphenyl, 2-naphthylamine, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, catechol, nitromethane, ethylene dioxide, acrylonitrile, ethylene carbamate, cadmium and polonium-240, tobacco specific nitrosamines (carcinogens), 4-(methylnitrosoamino)-1-(3-pyridyl)-1-butanone (NNK), N'-nitrosonornicotine (NNN), 4-(methylnitrosoamino)-1-(3-pyridyl)-1-butanol (NNAL) and its metabolite NNAL-glucuronide (measured in the urine of smokers and smokeless tobacco users) are most important^{4-6,9,11,12}.

Different corrective measures have been adopted to make smoking health friendly¹³ (by reducing nicotine, tar, toxic hydrocarbons, aldehydes, phenols, toxic metal contents etc. in smoke condensate or aerosols). One of the measures is introduction of filter tipped cigarettes containing different aerosol absorbent to reduce harmful constituents like nicotine, PAHs from smoke condensates.

Comparative studies on the efficiency of the filter beds of different brands of cigarettes (both Indian and Foreign make) in reducing nicotine and other ingredients have been reported in a recent paper¹³.

Attempt was made to ascertain the chemical constituents of the filter beds of the different brands of cigarettes and their effectiveness in arresting the extent of nicotine content and other harmful ingredients.

However, extensive research should be made to explore the different varieties of tobacco used in cigarettes, their cultivation pattern, origin etc. It is necessary to ascertain :

(i) The chemical compositions of tobaccos used in different brands and other ingredients used during cigarette elaboration by suitable solvent extraction processes.

(ii) To ascertain the chemical compositions of smoke condensates from burning different cigarettes under varied conditions and identify the harmful ingredients present in smoke condensate from tobacco and other internal ingredients.

(iii) To identify the metal contents of the cigarettes before and after burning to ascertain the extent of toxic

metal ingredients supposed to be absorbed by the body system.

Tobacco smoking is a health problem with a great impact on the society. Naturally, studies on the toxic chemicals in different varieties of tobacco and their origin are of forensic interest to apprehend culprits habituated with smoking particular brands of cigarettes^{14,15}. The studies also help the criminologists to establish smuggled/counterfeit cigarettes. A considerable revenue loss occurs due to use of counterfeit cigarettes. Moreover, studies of the metal contents in tobacco leaves and ashes as evidences of crime and positive signature of criminals i.e. studies are important from the point of view of forensic investigations and criminology^{14,15} though very little work has been done on these aspects.

The purposes of the present work are :

(i) To ascertain the ingredients in tobaccos in different brands of cigarettes, both Indian and Foreign brands (actually to ascertain their impact on health directly or indirectly) and the void in our approaches on tobacco products. The study is important from social point of view.

(ii) Studies on tobacco compositions in different brands of tobacco and try to ascertain the origin of the cigarettes to apprehend culprits or to establish smuggled/counterfeit cigarettes. This aspect has yet to be explored.

The results of the present investigation are described in this paper.

Materials and methods :

Chemicals :

Solvents like ethanol, methanol, acetone, dimethyl sulfoxide, ether and chloroform used were of HPLC grade from E. Merck.

Experimental materials were cigarettes of different brands purchased from the local market in Kolkata. USA make cigarettes were obtained as gifts from Mr. S. Lahiri, California. The name of the cigarettes and the countries of origin and other characteristics features are presented in Table 1. Four to five cigarettes of each brand were mixed properly to have representative samples for experimental purpose.

Table 1. Different brands of cigarettes with their country of origin, length of individual cigarette and length of filter

Sr. No.	Brand name of the cigarette	Country of origin	Length of the cigarette (cm)	Length of the filter (cm)
1.	Newport	USA	7.95	2.03
2.	Winston	USA	8.22	2.03
3.	Polmol	USA	8.20	Filterless
4.	Kool	USA	9.80	3.06
5.	Charms	India	6.86	1.04
6.	Wills Filter	India	7.43	2.04
7.	Popa	India	8.27	2.01
8.	Charminar	India	6.71	Filterless
9.	Tiptop	Bangladesh	8.30	1.11
10.	Dolphin	Myanmar, appeared to be counterfeit	8.35	1.95
11.	Ruili River	Not specified, appeared to be counterfeit	8.35	1.93

Experimental

Exactly 0.5 g of tobacco leaves each from different brands of cigarettes were taken in separate 10 mL of volumetric flasks, volumes made up to the mark in CHCl_3 with intermittent shaking and kept overnight. 6 μL of solution from each flask was injected (separately) in GC-MS to get the gas chromatogram. Each experiment was performed in triplicate. The chromatograms obtained under same condition were integrated to have the mass spectra of the selected brands of tobaccos. There were a large number of compounds in tobaccos in different brands of cigarettes. The ingredients in different brands of cigarettes were identified from total ion chromatograms (TIC) of GC-MS and mass spectra of the compounds. The compounds were also identified by proper library matching. However, some of the compounds were present in minute quantities and could not be identified.

Instrument :

Gas Chromatograph-Mass Spectrometer :

The identification and characterization of the compounds present were made using Perkin-Elmer Clarus 500 GC-MS by injecting 6 μL of the experimental solutions in chloroform through Elite 5MS column. Oven temperature was programmed between 70 °C (1 min) and 300 °C (10 min) with 10 °C/min increment, the injector and interface temperatures were 180 °C and 200 °C re-

spectively. The system was run at constant flow mode, the rate of carrier gas (helium) flow being 1 mL/min. MS parameters for the analysis were : EI mode, source temperature 150 °C, energy 70 eV, mass range scanned 30–400 a.m.u.

Results

The important ingredients of tobaccos in different brands of cigarettes are presented in Tables 2–5. TICs of tobaccos of different brands and mass spectra of some representative compounds are presented in Figs. 1–7.

Table 2. Some prominent compounds found in Tiptop cigarette from chloroform extract

Sr. No.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula
1.	9.67	Nicotine	162	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2$
2.	11.39	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	206	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$
3.	12.17	9-Octadecene	252	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{36}$
4.	12.63	Dodecanoic acid	200	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2$
5.	14.41	1-Nonadecene	266	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{38}$
6.	14.51	Tetradecanoic acid	228	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2$
7.	14.88	Neophytadiene	278	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{38}$
8.	15.79	Farnesyl acetone C	262	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}$
9.	16.45	Cyclotetracosane	336	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{48}$
10.	16.49	Hexadecanoic acid	256	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$
11.	18.32	1-Heneicosyl formate	340	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_2$
12.	18.36	Octadecanoic acid, ethyl ester	312	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_2$
13.	20.07	1-Eicosanol	298	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}$
14.	21.36	Di-iso-octylphthalate	390	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_4$
15.	21.71	1-Eicosanol	298	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}$
16.	22.54	Hentriacontane	436	$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{64}$
17.	23.31	1-Hentetracontanol	592	$\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{84}\text{O}$
18.	24.14	Tritetracontane	604	$\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{88}$
19.	24.72	Hexatriacontane	506	$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{74}$
20.	24.96	Tritetracontane	604	$\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{88}$
21.	25.90	Tetratetracontane	618	$\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{90}$
22.	26.10	Vitamin E	430	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_2$

Discussion

There are usually three different types of tobacco used for the preparation of cigarettes¹⁶.

(i) Flue Cured Virginia (FCV) Tobacco : aromatic and colourful processed tobacco.

(ii) Natu Tobacco : aromatic type sun cured tobacco, generally used to make cheaper brands of cigarettes.

Table 3. Some prominent compounds found in Dolphin cigarette from chloroform extract

Sl. No.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula
1.	9.44	Nicotine	162	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂
2.	11.41	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	206	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O
3.	12.18	1-Hexadecene	224	C ₁₆ H ₃₂
4.	12.79	Octadecanoic acid	284	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂
5.	13.42	Heptadecane-2,4,6,10,15-tetramethyl	296	C ₂₁ H ₄₄
6.	14.42	1-Nonadecene	266	C ₁₉ H ₃₈
7.	14.56	Tetradecanoic acid	228	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂
8.	14.88	Neophytadiene	278	C ₂₀ H ₃₈
9.	16.45	1-Nonadecene	266	C ₁₉ H ₃₈
10.	16.50	Hexadecanoic acid	256	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂
11.	18.32	1-Heneicosyl formate	340	C ₂₂ H ₄₄ O ₂
12.	18.36	Octadecanoic acid, ethyl ester	312	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O ₂
13.	20.03	1-Eicosanol	298	C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O
14.	20.87	Tetracosane	338	C ₂₄ H ₅₀
15.	21.33	Di-iso-octylphthalate	390	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄
16.	21.63	1-Eicosanol	298	C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O
17.	22.43	Hentriacontane	436	C ₃₁ H ₆₄
18.	23.15	Dichloroacetic acid, heptadecyl ester	366	C ₁₉ H ₃₆ O ₂ Cl ₂
19.	23.31	Squalene	410	C ₃₀ H ₅₀
20.	23.62	Hexatriacontane	506	C ₃₆ H ₇₄
21.	23.90	Hentriacontane	436	C ₃₁ H ₆₄
22.	24.43	Tritetracontane	604	C ₄₃ H ₈₈
23.	25.13	Tetratetracontane	618	C ₄₄ H ₉₀
24.	25.99	Vitamin E	430	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O ₂

Table 4. Some prominent compounds found in Newport cigarette from chloroform extract

Table-4 (contd.)

Sl. No.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula					
1.	7.10	Menthol	156	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ O	15.	21.64	1-Heneicosylformate	340	C ₂₂ H ₄₄ O ₂
2.	9.36	Nicotine	162	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂	16.	22.32	3,3'-Bi-p-menthone	278	C ₂₀ H ₃₈
3.	11.40	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	206	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O	17.	22.43	Hentriacontane	436	C ₃₁ H ₆₄
4.	12.20	1-Hexadecene	224	C ₁₆ H ₃₂	18.	23.16	1-Pentacontanol	718	C ₅₀ H ₁₀₂ O
5.	14.43	1-Nonadecene	266	C ₁₉ H ₃₈	19.	23.32	Squalene	410	C ₃₀ H ₅₀
6.	14.55	Tetradecanoic acid	228	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂	20.	23.91	Hentriacontane	436	C ₃₁ H ₆₄
7.	14.89	Neophytadiene	278	C ₂₀ H ₃₈	21.	24.44	Tetratriacontane	478	C ₃₄ H ₇₀
8.	16.46	1-Octanol	270	C ₁₈ H ₃₈ O	22.	25.15	Tetratetracontane	618	C ₄₄ H ₉₀
9.	18.23	9-Octadecanoic acid	282	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	23.	25.48	Pentatriacontane	492	C ₃₅ H ₇₂
10.	18.32	1-Tricosene	322	C ₂₃ H ₄₆	24.	25.99	Vitamin E	430	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O ₂
11.	18.36	Octadecanoic acid, ethyl ester	312	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O ₂					
12.	20.04	1-Eicosanol	298	C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O					
13.	20.88	Tetracosane	338	C ₂₄ H ₅₀					
14.	21.32	Di-iso-octylphthalate	390	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄					

(iii) Burley Tobacco : light air cured tobacco, ideal for cigarettes having high nicotine content with high absorbing capability for flavouring agents and additives.

There are also differences in compositions in different types depending on the places of origin and their biosynthetic pathways of production of tobacco. It is appa-

rent that tobacco undergoes substantial changes during growing, curing, processing and storing. During prepa-

Table 5. Some prominent compounds found in Charms cigarette from chloroform extract

Sl. No.	Retention time (min)	Name of the compounds	Molecular weight	Formula
1.	9.41	Nicotine	162	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂
2.	11.43	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	206	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ O
3.	12.22	3-Octadecene	252	C ₁₈ H ₃₆
4.	14.46	1-Nonadecene	266	C ₁₉ H ₃₈
5.	14.59	Tetradecanoic acid	228	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ O ₂
6.	14.92	Neophytadiene	278	C ₂₀ H ₃₈
7.	16.49	Cyclotetracosane	336	C ₂₄ H ₄₈
8.	18.20	Oleic acid	282	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂
9.	18.36	1-Tricosene	322	C ₂₃ H ₄₆
10.	20.08	1-Eicosanol	298	C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O
11.	20.93	Tetracosane	338	C ₂₄ H ₅₀
12.	21.35	1,2-Benzene dicarboxylic acid, di-iso-octyl ester	390	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄
13.	21.70	1-Octadecanol	270	C ₁₈ H ₃₈ O
14.	22.51	Nonacosane	408	C ₂₉ H ₅₀
15.	23.25	1-Heptacosanol	396	C ₂₇ H ₅₆ O
16.	23.41	Squalene	410	C ₃₀ H ₅₀
17.	23.74	Tritetracontane	604	C ₄₃ H ₈₈
18.	24.02	Tetratetracontane	618	C ₄₄ H ₉₀
19.	25.33	Tetratriacontane	478	C ₃₄ H ₇₀
20.	25.68	Hentriacontane	436	C ₃₁ H ₆₄
21.	26.17	Vitamin E	430	C ₂₉ H ₅₀ O ₂

ration of cigarettes, tobacco leaves, stems and other ingredients are blended to achieve a specific nicotine content, pH, taste, flavour and aroma. Alkaline pH makes nicotine bio-available. Nitrite contents or nitration during processing of tobacco increases harmful nitrosamines. Naturally, there should be wide variation in the composition of tobaccos and other ingredients in different brands of cigarettes.

Nicotine was invariably present in large amounts in all brands of cigarettes with neophytadine as the second largest component. The peak areas of the two compounds were measured. Nicotine and neophytadine were chosen as representative compounds for the measurements of peak areas. Peak area of 1-nonadecene was also taken as representative of other hydrocarbons. The results are presented in Table 6.

The results show a considerable variation in nicotine contents of the cigarettes and at least three different brands of tobacco are used. However, in order to know the origin of tobacco in different cigarettes, isotopic signatures or isotopic ratios of C, N or O were utilized. The specific instruments for the purpose are IR-MS or Isotopic ratio Mass Spectroscopy, which are not available. Sharma and Lahiri determined the isotopic masses of N, C etc. in different explosives using FTIR measurements at 77 K with MCT detector¹⁷. In this work, no attempt has been

Fig. 1. TIC of chloroform extract of Tiptop cigarette.

Fig. 2. TIC of chloroform extract of Charms cigarette.

Fig. 3. TIC of chloroform extract of Wills cigarette.

Fig. 4. TIC of chloroform extract of Newport cigarette.

Fig. 5. Mass spectrum of nicotine obtained from a cigarette.

Fig. 6. Mass spectrum of menthol obtained from a cigarette.

Fig. 7. Mass spectrum of 2,4-di-t-butylphenol obtained from a cigarette.

Table 6. Peak areas of nicotine and peak area percentages of nicotine, neophytadiene and 1-nonadecene in different brands of cigarettes

Sr. No.	Brand name	Nicotine area counts	Nicotine peak area (%)	Neophytadiene peak area (%)	1-Nonadecene peak area (%)	Other components peak area (%)
1.	Ruili River	50939340	62.54	8.73	2.21	26.52
2.	Tiptop	27881592	39.88	4.31	3.10	52.71
3.	Dolphin	42459088	58.78	7.97	2.66	30.59
4.	Newport	70708208	65.12	7.83	1.07	25.98
5.	Popa	52757704	57.82	4.26	2.03	35.89
6.	Winston	50435852	52.52	8.18	1.59	37.71
7.	Kool	51918520	51.17	5.71	1.39	41.73
8.	Polmol	56135644	57.46	6.68	1.84	34.02
9.	Charminar	38249680	58.12	5.95	3.23	32.70
10.	Charms	240455436	40.14	8.05	2.0	49.81
11.	Wills	30167010	50.99	5.80	2.29	40.92

made to determine isotopic ratios of N, C and H etc. in tobacco leaves but the total variations in isotopic masses in nicotine using GC-MS and measurement in SIM mode was made. The mass number of nicotine is 162. Hence, the relative abundances of nicotine using 162 (as 100%), 163 and 164 are determined by injecting 2 μ L solution for measurement at 163 and 6 μ L solution for measurement at 164. Results are presented in Tables 7–9. Sensitivity for abundance at 164 must be low. Representative figures are given in Figs. 8–10.

The measurements of nicotine counts (Table 6) and relative abundance at 163 clearly show that at least three different varieties of tobacco were utilised. The survey of literature on isotopic signature of compounds at different places should provide the answer. However, survey of literature showed 3900 compounds are available, obviously many of the ingredients were not from tobacco but the burning products of tobaccos and other ingredients used and produced from them.

Moreover, ingredients determined are dependent on extraction process of tobacco leaves using solvents under varied conditions. Hexane or cyclohexane extracts are

Table 7. Average area counts of different isotopes of nicotine in different brands of cigarettes

Sr. No.	Brand name	Average area counts for the mass 162	Average area counts for the mass 163	Average area counts for the mass 164
1.	Newport (USA)	155234	17554	128
2.	Winston (USA)	87197	5142	77
3.	Polmol (USA)	86665	5250	90
4.	Charms (India)	105357	7424	94
5.	Wills Filter (India)	106580	6657	94
6.	Popa (India)	91990	5416	88
7.	Tiptop (Bangladesh)	77408	6178	63
8.	Dolphin (Myanmar, appeared to be counterfeit)	122177	9242	110

found to give more hydrocarbons whereas extractions by CH_2Cl_2 under specific conditions give nitrosamines obtainable in tobacco leaves. Moreover, nitrosamines can be obtained during nitrosation of nicotine by interaction with saliva and liver.

The column length and temperature applied are also

important. Thus most of the works can be regarded not to be exhaustive.

Table 8. Relative area counts of isotopes having mass number 163 and 164 in respect of mass number 162 of nicotine in different brands of cigarettes

Sr. No.	Brand name	Average abundance of mass 162	Average abundance of mass 163	Average abundance of mass 164
1.	Newport (USA)	100	11.30	0.086
2.	Winston (USA)	100	5.89	0.088
3.	Polmol (USA)	100	6.05	0.103
4.	Charms (India)	100	7.04	0.089
5.	Wills Filter (India)	100	6.24	0.088
6.	Popa (India)	100	5.88	0.095
7.	Tiptop (Bangladesh)	100	7.98	0.081
8.	Dolphin (Myanmar, appeared to be counterfeit)	100	7.56	0.090

Table 9. Isotope ratio as per NIST library of isotopes having mass number 163 and 164 in respect of mass number 162 of nicotine

Average abundance for the mass 162	Average abundance for the mass 163	Average abundance for the mass 164
100	12.05	0.66

In order to understand the efficiency of filter, it is necessary to determine the ingredients present in tobacco leaves and ingredients used during elaboration of cigarettes of different brands. It is also necessary to know accurately the ingredients present in tobacco smokes condensates for which cigarettes must be submitted to a smoke procedure with a smoking machine in proper air circulation with conditions similar to those used in the smoking way of usual smokers. The ingredients should be analysed by solvent extraction of the condensates in suitable solvents or by other analytical procedures. The ashes should be utilised to determine metal constituents¹⁴.

In a previous paper¹³, reports were made on the comparative studies on the efficiency of filters of different brands of cigarettes in reducing nicotine and other ingredients.

However, it is really difficult to determine the real efficiency in terms of nicotine content as a large number of factors are involved as given below :

(i) Total amount of nicotine and other ingredients present in tobacco in different brands of cigarettes are variable. Various ingredients are used during cigarette preparation and elaboration.

(ii) Nicotine and other ingredients particularly PAHs,

Fig. 8. SIM of Dolphin cigarette at mass number 162.

Fig. 9. SIM of Dolphin cigarette at mass number 163.

Fig. 10. SIM of Dolphin cigarette at mass number 164.

phenols must be converted to a large number of other products during burning and the amount of nicotine, PAHs in smoke condensate must be known to ascertain the efficiency of filter. The natures of burning patterns are variable depending on the users and the number of puffs taken.

(iii) Amount of smoke condensate thrown to the atmosphere is not known.

(iv) Nicotine and other substances extracted must be dependant on solvent and the condition and other factors of extraction. It is to be noted that ingredients extracted in different solvents cannot be true indices of the compounds actually absorbed in the body as the solvents are not biological solvents and were not extracted under human conditions of temperature and pressure.

It is thus a far cry to determine the efficiency in terms of nicotine removal. A partial attempt has been made to estimate the amount of nicotine removed by comparing the total nicotine content of the tobacco present in different cigarettes and the nicotine contents absorbed in the filters (though the removal of other hazardous chemicals are also important).

Nicotine content of tobacco in cigarettes and the filter beds may give a rough idea regarding the removal of nicotine and other ingredients present in cigarettes. Actually removal of the nicotine contents and other harmful ingredients in tobacco smoke condensates by the filter beds should determine the efficiency of filters.

In our survey of literature^{18,19}, the ingredients coming from tobacco smoke appear to be full of controversial facts. In general, most of the organic compounds are converted to ashes, CO₂ and other gaseous ingredients at about 450 °C. Naturally, there should be definite curiosity how nicotine and other compounds survived in the

temperature ranges like 300–950 °C of cigarettes burning. There are other factors which need further examination. Our work is the beginning in this direction.

References

1. Report on Oral Tobacco use and its implications in South East India, WHO SEARO, 2004, Chap. 1, Oral Tobacco Products, pp. 6-20.
2. "The Scientific basis of Tobacco Product Regulation", WHO Technical Report Series, 2007, **945**, Chaps. 1-5, pp. 1-96.
3. A. Jemal, M. J. Thun, Lynn A. G. Ries, H. L. Howe, H. K. Weir, M. M. Center, E. Ward, Xiao-Cheng Wu, C. Ehemann, R. Anderson, U. A. Ajani, B. Kohler and B. K. Edwards, *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.*, 2008, **100**, 1672.
4. Smokeless Tobacco and some Tobacco specific N-nitrosamines, IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Human, Vol. 89, Lyon, France, 2007.
5. S. S. Hecht, *Chem. Res. Toxicol.*, 2008, **21**, 160.
6. S. S. Hecht, *Nat. Rev. Cancer*, 2003, **3**, 733.
7. T. Norgrandy and D. F. Weaver, "Medicinal Chemistry – A Molecular and Biochemical approach", 3rd ed., Oxford University Press, 2005, pp. 205-206, 320, 480, 505.
8. Goodman and Gilman, in : L. L. Brunton, J. S. Lazo and K. L. Parker (eds.), "The Pharmacological basis of Therapeutics", 11th ed., McGraw Hill, Medical Publishing Division, New York, 2006, pp. 1753.
9. R. R. Baker, E. D. Massey and G. Smith, *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 2004, **425**, 553.
10. M. F. Fadzil and N. M. Tahir, *The Malaysian J. of Anal. Sci.*, 2007, **11**, 1.
11. I. Stepanov, S. S. Hecht, S. Ramakrishnan and P. C. Gupta, *Int. J. Cancer*, 2005, **116**, 16.
12. D. Hoffmann and S. S. Hecht, *Cancer Research*, 1985, **45**, 935.
13. A. Chakraborty and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2013, **90**, 1383.
14. J. L. Perez-Bernal, J. M. Amigo, R. Fernandez-Torres, M. A. Bello and M. Callejon-Mochon, *Forensic Science International*, 2011, **204**, 119.
15. Conan-Doyle, in : E. Glinert (ed.), "The Adventures

- and Memories of Sherlock Holmes", Penguin Group, Penguin Books Ltd., London, 2001.
16. V. M. Sivaramakrishnan, "Tobacco and areca nut", Orient Longmans, Chennai, 2001.
17. S. P. Sharma and S. C. Lahiri, *J. Energetic Materials*, 2005, **23**, 1.
18. S. J. Stohs, D. Bagchi and M. Bagchi, *Toxicol.*, 1997, **9**, 867.
19. S. Landsberger and D. Wu, *Sci. Total Environ.*, 1995, **173-174**, 323.